

THE FORMATION OF UPCOMING ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS' SPEECH CULTURES

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Abstract: The article's significance is based on the necessity of developing inventive skills in aspiring elementary school teachers in order to get them ready to undertake creative activities. The training of creative, capable instructors who can carry out their professional activities utilizing the required, efficient teaching materials and innovations in education is emphasized as one of the pressing pedagogical issues.

Key words: innovation, technology, competence, innovative process, innovative education, technical tools, competence, modern education, lifelong learning, SMART technology.

In the world, scientific and research work is being carried out on the issues of expanding the possibility of forming the innovative competence of future primary school teachers, the wide use of information and communication technology tools in the system, and the development of creative models of the pedagogical process aimed at the formation of innovative competence. It is also important to reveal the motivational effect of encouraging pedagogical features such as inquisitiveness, ingenuity and research in preparing future primary school teachers for the formation of their innovative competence. The development of the education system in our country characterized by the increasing role of innovative technologies, directing young specialists to innovative activities, activating their motivation for quality education, reconsidering the place and role of innovative activities in educational institutions, implementing educational reforms forecasting the growth process in accordance with the priority directions of socio-economic development of the regions is recognized as an urgent problem. Today, the globalization process requires the training of competitive, inquisitive, competent personnel according to its social and cultural essence. The use of innovative technologies in the educational process increases the quality of education and students' interest in the profession, and increases the effectiveness of pedagogues. In Shuorin, our president Sh. Mirziyoyev's "Our young people have independent thinking, high intellectual and spiritual potential, and in order for them to mature and be happy as people who are equal to their peers on a global scale in any field, mobilize all the strength and capabilities of our state and society." etamiz"1 directly correspond to the purpose and mission of our work. In the pedagogical literature, the terms "Innovative education", "Innovative process" and "Innovative activity" were rarely observed in the recent past. The concept of "innovative education" was first used in 1979 at the "Club of Rome". At the root of this word is the complex activity of organizing innovations in education, their assimilation, use of innovations and their manifestation. Innovative education is an opportunity for the learner to create new thoughts, ideas, norms, and rules, to develop qualities and skills related to the natural acceptance of advanced ideas, norms, and rules created by other people. education that creates. The technologies used in the process of innovative education are called educational innovations or innovative educational technologies. Educational innovations are forms, methods, technologies that can be used to solve existing problems in the field of education or the educational process based on a new approach, and can achieve much more effective

results than before. Innovative process in the field of education is a concept of education, innovations and changes in the curriculum, education and teaching methods, methods and methods. In the original meaning of the word innovative processes in the field of education lies the problem of the pedagogue's learning, generalization and popularization of advanced pedagogical experiences and the practical implementation of the achievements of pedagogical sciences. "Competence" and "competence" are mutually different concepts: competence is a general description of a specialist's professionalism, regardless of personal qualities. It exists separately from the official, its direct bearer, and needs possession. Competence is personally acquired competence, expression of "person in profession". By innovative competence, we understand a certain level of manifestation of the personal and professional skills of the pedagogue in his innovative activity. In other words, innovative competence is the result of the theoretical and practical preparation of the pedagogue for the implementation of professional activities using educational and effective innovations. Currently, the use of SMART technologies in the educational process gives effective results. SMART (smart, intelligent, technological) is an acronym, which is essentially a new educational environment. First used by Paul J. Meyer in 1965 and then by George T. Doran in 1981 in his academic work, SMART empowers teachers, professionals, and students to use global knowledge and move from passive content to active content. that is, to combine educational activities. The advantages of using SMART technology in the educational process for teachers and students are as follows: - Innovative approach to the presentation of educational material; - Rapid feedback with students; - Formation of a unified real and virtual world; - Easy learning process. management;-Maximum variety of multimedia;-Common informational educational environment;-A large number of sources of information;-Easy management of the educational process;-Quick and simple determination of students' ability according to their needs and level; - Opportunity to establish cooperation with several educational institutions and create a network for information exchange; - Fast feedback with the increase in the speed and quality of education; - Development of creativity and opportunities for independent implementation; - Depending on the location and time The possibility of obtaining the necessary information in different conditions; - The possibility of giving permission to start studying for preparation in any situation. To implement SMART-education, first of all, high-speed Internet that provides maximum mobility to ensure use anywhere, at any time, pedagogues have a mature level of technological competence, automation of the educational process and modern technologicalization is necessary... In the current period, it is necessary to increase the efficiency of education, to direct the teaching staff to innovative activities, to develop the level of professional competence of specialists, to apply innovative education and information and communication technologies to the educational process in higher education institutions, to advance or assimilation of foreign experiences and targeted orientation can be considered as urgent tasks in the higher education system.

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INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY